

Barabasch, A. (2019). Understanding creativity as an occupation specific competence. In F. Marhuenda & M.J. Chisvert-Tarazona (Eds.), *Pedagogical concerns and market demands in VET. Proceedings of the 3rd Crossing Boundaries in VET conference, Vocational Education and Training Network (VETNET)* (pp.418-422) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2640966>

Understanding creativity as an occupation specific competence

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Keywords

workplace learning; creativity; competence; vocational training; innovation

1 Inconceivable workplace changes with surmountable challenges to VET

Particularly relevant within vocational education and training (VET) in Switzerland is the acquisition of skills that support workers in seeking new solutions to workplace challenges, which means to think and act creatively. This new requirement is also reinforced by the development and introduction of new technologies, which will replace workers in some fields and will require new jobs in others. Switzerland is considered an innovation leader in the world with about 90% of innovation taking place within the industry (SWIR 2015). Its research infrastructure and strong apprenticeship system are guarantors for this success. In fact, more than 70% of each cohort complete a vocational education and training (VET) program at secondary II level (SBFI 2018a). Taking into consideration that many innovative ideas come from workers at the lower hierarchical levels within an enterprise it signals that this level of education is highly valued in the country and supports innovation (GAN, Accenture and ETH 2017). Accordingly, VET is particularly challenged to support the development of creative thinking skills and action competence, abilities that can be expected to support individuals in managing their careers successfully and advancing professionally through their creative contributions at the workplace.

Creativity is a very complex phenomenon, possibly a competence and not just the sum of various components. Erpenbeck, Sauter, and Werner (2016) argued that “competences are the skills to act in unpredicted, open-ended, sometimes chaotic situations creatively and self-organized.” Caroff and Lubart (2012) have been specifically concerned with the psychological resources for creativity. They claim that individuals’ capacity to be creative is a latent ability that can be solicited. Referring to Lubarts’ and others earlier work (Lubart et al., 2003), various attributes necessary for creativity have been identified, which are a combination of cognitive, conative and environmental attributes.

According to the vocational competences model by Rauner, Heinemann and Maurer (2013) vocational competence is compiled of job- related, personal and social competence. The (holistic) completion of a vocational task requires a number of further competences, such as presentation/form/clarity, functionality, efficiency, sustainability, work- and process-knowledge, environmental compatibility, social acceptability and creativity. The authors conclude that apprentices need to be educated to acquire these competences.

Although, apprentices are learners who need to build up skills and competences, they are also a source of ideas that enterprises can build on when further developing their existing products or even working on radical innovations. Enterprises are increasingly discovering the creative potential of their staff and support new forms of work collaboration that help to unleash this potential and lead to innovations. Curricula frameworks for vocational training programs start to address creativity development as one competence development goal (Barabasch 2018a, 2018b). Amabile (1987) found a variety of skills that are relevant to pro-

duce work that is original, such as suspending judgment, self-discipline, perseverance and nonconformity. Also eagerness to work diligently is considered to be an essential component of high levels of creativity (Golann 1963). While productivity and effectiveness are driving forces at the workplace, it helps apprentices to be provided with room to explore and play either at school or a protected space at the workplace. Particularly supportive is the participation in teams that work creatively and develop innovations as much as the possibility to create individual projects with the provision of sufficient time and a realistic framework of expectations to realize them.

2 Creativity development in the professions

Conclusions from various studies on profession specific creativity development suggest the need to understand creativity and creative potential in a domain-specific perspective as differences emerge across the professional fields. Not much is known yet about creativity development within professions for which an apprenticeship would be the entry point. Similarly to the notion of competence, the ways in which individuals put in act their potential depends on various contextual factors including the required abilities related to each specific task. It is well known that different abilities are required in different job domains depending on particular work tasks that are typical of each domain.

There is a huge amount of scientific publications on creativity assessment and a multitude of instruments have been developed and well described in numerous review studies. As reported by Barbot and colleagues (2011) instruments for creativity assessment can be differentiated in relation to the main research question on creativity they refer to, that are in turn related to the conceptual ideas on creativity. A first set of instruments explores creativity as exclusively related to giftedness or talent. Those instruments would address the question: Is this individual creative? Differently, authors adopting a componential approach are mainly interested in answering the question: How creative is this individual? A third approach relies on the main assumption that all individuals have a creative potential which is differently shaped and can be put in action depending on the contextual conditions. Also this potential can be identified and nurtured. This approach mainly focuses on the following question: “How is this student creative?” The question is strongly related to pedagogical questions being asked when designing classroom instruction in VET as well as didactical considerations in VET teacher training. It builds on the belief, that creativity can be taught and developed as well as on the assumption that creative performance is required in different ways in different professional domains.

3 The case of the telecommunication industry – understanding creativity in the context of work and learning

Since early 2018 a case study that inquires about innovative apprenticeship practice in the telecommunication industry has been underway. It focuses on how apprentices in initial vocational education are socialized within a new learning culture and how they acquire the competencies relevant for their working careers as well as for a specific occupation. A key issue in the study is how the creative potential of apprentices can be unleashed and incorporated into the development of innovations. Representatives of all groups involved in VET have been interviewed: coaches, supervisors, VET managers and apprentices. In total the presentation reports on the base of 20 semi-structured interviews with apprentices in various VET programmes at this enterprise lasting 30 to 60 minutes. They were conducted in three language regions (German, French and Italian).

Interviews partially were concerned with facts in respect to the learning experience and in addition, by asking open-ended questions, initiated narrations about individual experiences,

perceptions and ideas. The first part of the data interpretation was based on the documentary method according to Bohnsack (2003). Emerging themes and subthemes have been identified on the level of ‘immanent sense making’. It refers to consequently remaining on the relevance system of an individual as well as the group of apprentices. We looked for text sections in the transcripts that present a picture or are metaphorical. Based on these findings the team started a process of reflective interpretation.

The empirical base provides insights into the experiences of apprentices within a learning culture that supports creativity in various ways. The data further provide information about attitudes, values, beliefs and practices among all stakeholders within the company regarding the support of creativity at the workplace. Overall, the study intends to increase the understanding of the role of innovative learning cultures within the preparation of future workers at Swiss enterprises, taking apprenticeships and their creativity development in the focus of attention. The research was guided by the following questions:

- How is an innovation culture realized within apprenticeships?
- How are creativity, individuality and flexibility of the apprentices supported?
- Which challenges are faced in enterprises within the new learning culture (e.g. in respect to coaching, apprenticeship planning, management of place and time, media usage and development, communication and relationship management?)

Gathered data allowed the team of researchers to develop a list of measures that can be implemented within an apprenticeship to unleash the creative potential of apprentices and to gain insights how these measures function and act within a particular learning culture. This case study approach has rarely been applied within VET research and promises to provide new insights into the complexity of the functioning of the VET system. The theoretical foundations for studying the case are interdisciplinary and come from economics, organizational psychology, sociology as well as education.

4 Innovative learning cultures in VET and creativity support

Within the enterprise creative thinking and acting has been viewed as an important step towards innovation and the different work arrangements and projects often require creative work. Generally, creativity is viewed as a mental and social process to generate ideas, concepts and associations (Serrat 2017). A very important factor in acting creatively is risk taking behavior, which is relevant when developing new products and processes and which supports creative work (Sternberg et al. 1997). At the enterprise the willingness to take risk is supported by a transparent and constructive way of communicating. In regular meetings the apprentices receive feedback about their behavior and performance and have the possibility to speak about their concerns and difficulties. A trustful relationship with their coaches also enables a culture of mistakes, in which apprentices realize that making mistakes is an essential part of their learning process. The study provides numerous examples of apprentices making mistakes and how their coaches helped them to make sense of it and how to learn from their experience.

In the following areas creativity can be supported within the enterprise. A positive culture of encouraging and communicating about mistakes, trustful relationships and a communication at eye level reduce fear and insecurity and support self-efficacy and self-reflexivity. That making mistakes and experimentation is supported in the enterprise is also expressed by one apprentice:

„A mistake is... well, we have hang up a poster there. Making a mistake is better, than not doing anything. I only learn when I do something, when I try something out. If I make a

mistake, chances are that for about 90% I am not doing it again. Here at the company they say you better make a mistake than you never even try to do something.”

Overall, the company is strongly supporting that apprentices have a large room for maneuver and can try out many different tasks and workplace situations. Through the market place at which they chose projects to work in, their learning pathway throughout the apprenticeship can be shaped in a very individualized way (see Barabasch 2019; Caldart & Barabasch 2019; an extension of this section is foreseen in the presentation and the final paper).

5 Conclusion

The findings of the study refer to a large range of measures that companies have or could have available to guarantee their students' creative work and the possibility to shape their learning pathway throughout their apprenticeship in a somewhat creative way. In an extension of the paper these measures will be explained and it will be shown what effect they have on apprentices competence development. Research says that transferal skills are increasingly important (Moraal, 2009) and personal competences (e.g. creativity and independence) as well. The telecommunication industry is because of its confrontation with technological changes constantly in a state of agility and continuously needs to update their approach to apprenticeship training as much as apprentice recruitment and approaches to social support.

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Biographical note

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